

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

**Offshore Observations Special Interest Group
Topical Workshop Report**

October 27, 2025

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CRESCENT Topical Workshop Report Offshore Observations

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Much of the Cascadia subduction zone, the future site of a major megathrust earthquake, lies offshore. Many scientific questions centered on the unique characteristics of Cascadia, including the lack of interplate seismicity and mixed vergence of faulting in the accretionary wedge, require near-field offshore observations to investigate. However, working in the offshore requires far more funding and collaboration than equivalent onshore experiments. To help communicate, advance, and coordinate offshore research efforts in Cascadia, an Offshore Observations special interest group (OO SIG) was formed within the Cascadia Regional Science Center (CRESCENT).¹

The OO SIG gathered for its first in-person meeting on October 27, 2025 in Seattle at the University of Washington, bringing together ~70 geoscientists from many institutions and career stages.² The goal of the meeting was to highlight the diversity of offshore science related to CRESCENT, provide an opportunity for networking, and discuss opportunities for future collaborations and synergies that could be fostered by the OO SIG. Over 30 short research talks, organized into five topics, provided an update on the current state of offshore investigations in Cascadia. Organic discussion and organized breakout groups then allowed for some synthesis of the shared research and potential use-cases for the OO SIG. Here, we summarize the highlights from this meeting and suggest next steps for the OO SIG.

The research talks, which made up the majority of the meeting, were organized into five main topics. Here we summarize the main concepts and techniques presented in each:

1. Structure of the incoming plate
 - a. Topics: Vp/Vs ratio of incoming plate; thermal structure of the subduction zone, along-dip variations in material properties; relationship between structural properties and megathrust locking state
 - b. Techniques: passive and active seismic imaging using ocean bottom seismometer network; thermal modeling
2. Megathrust locking and shallow slow slip

¹ See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/offshore-observations/>

² See <https://cascadiaquakes.org/2025/09/09/offshore-observations-topical-workshop/>

- a. Topics: current locking state of the shallow subduction zone; shallow slow slip events
- b. Techniques: geodesy using a variety of sensors - borehole pressure sensors, absolute pressure gauges, and a novel optical fiber strainmeter; reanalysis of onshore tremor and geodetic catalogs
3. Accretionary wedge deformation
 - a. Topics: structure and location/types of faults in the accretionary wedge; anticipated coseismic slip activity near the deformation front/on splay faults
 - b. Techniques: active seismic data processing; structural modeling
4. Fluid pathways and hydrology
 - a. Topics: fluid flow pathways along subduction zone plate boundary, forearc faults, and to the seafloor; amount of fluid in the forearc and its effect on strength of the forearc
 - b. Techniques: mineral and pore fluid sampling; seismic full waveform inversion; ambient noise imaging using ocean bottom seismometers; active seismic imaging; fluid sampling from seeps using ROVs
5. Future offshore observations
 - a. Topics: proposed targets for seafloor drilling; planned expansion of cabled instrumentation; opportunities for fiber optic sensing on existing cables; planned GNSS-A instrumentation; challenges associated with shoreline-crossing imaging
 - b. Techniques: borehole sensing; coring; distributed acoustic sensing; collocated cabled instruments (absolute pressure gauges and ocean bottom seismometers); GNSS-A

Following these sessions, brief breakout discussions focused on distilling priority science questions, which types of data are most needed, geographic regions that can serve as targets, potential useful collaborations, and future directions of the OOSIG.

The main scientific questions that were continually highlighted can be largely grouped under two main categories:

Interseismic – what is the current distribution of locking on the Cascadia megathrust?

- Does shallow slow slip occur offshore?
- Where do fluids travel along the subduction zone?
- What is the material strength and thermal state of the megathrust in different regions?
- Where are segmentation boundaries?
- How does the structure of the incoming plate influence locking distribution?

Coseismic – how will slip be distributed in the next megathrust event in Cascadia?

- Where and what type of faults exist in the accretionary wedge?
- What is the material strength of the shallow megathrust and accretionary wedge, and do we expect megathrust slip to extend to the deformation front?

- Do locking segmentation boundaries relate to megathrust rupture boundaries?

To work towards these questions, the following data targets were emphasized:

- Collocated instruments: combining seismometers, multiple types of geodesy (pressure gauges, borehole sensing, fiber-optic strain sensing), distributed acoustic sensing, fluid sampling, and subsurface geophysical imaging all at the same sites
- Expanded geodesy: more seafloor GNSS-A sites, particularly near the deformation front and in under-sampled regions such as the incoming plate
- Seafloor drilling: the installation of boreholes to observe transient deformation and overall strength of the inner and outer wedge and incoming plate
- Expanded high-resolution imaging: 3D seismic surveys in under sampled regions, more processing of existing data to yield improved S-wave velocity models, thermal models, and attenuation structure
- Continuous, long-term monitoring: more instrumentation on existing cabled observatories, taking advantage of commercially available fiber optic cables for distributed acoustic sensing

The following geographic regions were emphasized as targets:

- The northernmost and southernmost extent of the subduction zone: Canada and California are more difficult to permit in. These portions were largely left out of the recent large-scale CASIE active seismic survey.
- Crossing the shoreline: where is the slab near the coast?
- The incoming plate: detailed active seismic surveys using ocean bottom seismometers (similar to the CASIE-21 experiment) would be useful to illuminate the deep structure of the incoming plate and what is going into the subduction zone.

What role can the OOSIG play going forward?

A repeated sentiment that arose from the breakout groups and general discussion was the value of having many scientists in-person, in one room, with focused time to share recent work and ideas. The convenience of having this one-day meeting tied to a larger meeting was also emphasized. This can be a primary use for the OOSIG going forward: the facilitation of in-person, annual-scale meetings where current offshore research is shared between many scientists across disciplines.

A secondary purpose for the OOSIG can be to coordinate smaller focused groups with clear goals, adapting to form new groups as opportunities arise. Examples of subgroup focuses that were discussed in the breakout section include:

- Placement of GNSS-A sites for the SZ4D initiative
- Community priorities for offshore geodesy and related observations (e.g., ocean bottom seismometer deployments to detect shallow tremor)
- Planning for offshore earthquake rapid response

- Collocated instrument and imaging proposals
- Coordinated targets for DAS deployments on commercial cables or planned construction (i.e., wind farms)
- GNSS-A processing techniques

Appendix A: Meeting Agenda

AGENDA

8:30 am: Workshop check-in and light continental breakfast

9:00 am: Welcome and opening remarks *presented by* **Zoe Krauss, Anna Ledeczi, and Brandon Shuck**

9:15 am: **Structure of the Incoming Plate**

“Vp/Vs Structure of the Juan de Fuca Plate from Converted-Phase Tomography of the Ridge-to-Trench Dataset” *presented by* **Hanchao Jian**, Research Associate III, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution

“An Update on the Pacific Coast Seismic Assessment of Faults and Earthquakes (PACSAFE) Project” *presented by* **Tiegan Hobbs**, Research Scientist / Adjunct Professor Geological Survey of Canada / The University of British Columbia / University of Victoria

“Imaging Along-Dip Variations in Material Properties of the Subducted Crust and Their Link to Megathrust Fault Coupling in Southern Cascadia” *presented by* **Hao Guo**, Research Scientist, University of Wisconsin – Madison

“First Steps Towards a Shallow Thermal Structure Model for the Cascadia Subduction Zone” *presented by* **Magali Isabelle Billen**, Professor, University of California – Davis

10:00 am: Coffee break

10:15 am: **Constraints on Megathrust Locking State and Shallow Slow Slip**

“Deep-sea Borehole Observations Reveal Strain Accumulation due to Megathrust Locking: Cascadia and Beyond” *presented by* **Tianhaozhe Sun**, Research Scientist / Adjunct Assistant Professor, Geological Survey of Canada / University of Victoria

“Searching for shallow tectonic tremor offshore Cascadia” *presented by* **Zoe Krauss**, Postdoctoral Researcher, Pacific Northwest Seismic Network / University of Washington

“Using Episodic Tremor and Slip to Characterize Segmentation Boundaries in Northern Cascadia” *presented by* **Alaura Custard**, University of Kansas

“Shallow slow slip events at the Hikurangi Subduction Zone documented in IODP borehole observatories” *presented by* **McKenzie Carlson**, Graduate Student, The University of Texas at Austin

“Plate motion velocities offshore of northern Cascadia from five years of seafloor geodesy with the NCSZO” *presented by* **Jesse Hutchinson**, Staff Scientist, Ocean Networks Canada

“Understanding shallow creep in the stress shadow of megathrust locked zone: Cascadia vs. Nankai” *presented by* **Kelin Wang**, Research Scientist, Geological Survey of Canada

“Detection of shallow slow slip with a seafloor optical fiber strainmeter” *presented by* **Noel Jackson**, Assistant Professor, University of Kansas

11:30 am: **Accretionary Wedge Deformation**

“Evidence for megathrust locking and shallow coseismic slip in the Cascadia accretionary wedge” *presented by* **Harold Tobin**

“Submarine canyon slope failure during the 1700 earthquake: evidence from sediment cores and seismic data” *presented by* **Evan Lahr**, University of Washington

“Improving offshore splay fault geometries and slip histories using seismic data reprocessing and structural modeling” *presented by* **Anna Ledeczi**, Ph.D. Candidate, University of Washington

12:15 pm: Lunch provided

1:15 pm: **Fluid Pathways and Hydrology of Subduction Zones**

“Subduction zone fluid flow: direct evidence from mineral & water samples” *presented by* **Man-Yin Tsang**, University of Saskatchewan

“Seismic full waveform inversion (FWI) can help improve understanding of SZ geology, geophysics, geomechanics and fluid flow” *presented by* **David Lumley**, Professor / Department Head, The University of Texas at Dallas

“Active Protothrusts and Fluid Highways: Seismic Noise Reveals Hidden Subduction Dynamics in Cascadia” *presented by* **Maleen Kidiwela**, University of Washington

“The Strength of the Sedimentary Wedge Along the Cascadia Subduction Zone” *presented by* **Shuoshuo Han**, Assistant Research Professor, University of Texas Institute for Geophysics

“Unraveling Fluid/Methane Seeps at the Cascadia Subduction Zone” *presented by* **Jeffrey Beeson**, Assistant Professor, Oregon State University

2:15 pm: **Plans for Future Offshore Observations**

“The Cascadia Cabled Borehole Observatories Proposal for Scientific Ocean Drilling” *presented by* **Harold Tobin**, Professor, University of Washington

“Multiplexed DAS on the OOI RCA” *presented by* **Ethan Williams**, Assistant Professor, University of California – Santa Cruz

“ONC’s Offshore Observatories: Status and Roadmap for Infrastructure enabling Subduction Zone Science and Realtime Monitoring” *presented by* **Martin Heesemann**, Senior Staff Scientist, Ocean Networks Canada

“Strengthening Tsunami Early Warning in Indonesia through Offshore Observations and EEWS Integration” *presented by* **Buha Mujur Mandela Simamora**, Master of Science, Indonesia Agency for Meteorology Climatology and Geophysics

“The Cascadia Offshore Subduction Zone Observatory” *presented by* **William Wilcock**, Jerome M. Paros Endowed Chair in Sensor Networks, University of Washington

“Offshore Science Goals and Observational Strategies for Cascadia” *presented by* **David Schmidt**, Professor, University of Washington

“Crossing the Coastline in Cascadia and Beyond: Persistent Barriers and Promising Directions” *presented by* **Helen Janiszewski**, Assistant Professor, University of Hawai‘i at Mānoa

3:15 pm: Break

3:30 pm: Breakout discussions

Discussion Questions:

- What do you see as priority questions for offshore Cascadia earthquake science?
- What types of offshore observations are missing and/or least understood and critical to earthquake science in Cascadia?
- What industry/agency connections could help improve our understanding of offshore Cascadia?
- What cross-disciplinary scientific collaborations would be most valuable to answering outstanding questions centered on the offshore?
- What are ideal science goals for the OO-SIG in the upcoming years? What format of future meetings and activities would be most useful?

4:30 pm: Closing remarks

5:00 pm: Workshop concludes

Appendix B: Meeting Participants

WORKSHOP REGISTRANTS

Eiichiro Araki, Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology
Asif Ashraf, University of Oregon
Luciana Astiz, United States National Science Foundation
Dan Bassett, Earth Sciences New Zealand
Jeffrey Beeson, Oregon State University
Magali Billen, University of California - Davis
Paul Bodin, University of Washington
Joseph Byrnes, University of Texas at Dallas
McKenzie Carlson, The University of Texas at Austin
Joshua Church, Louisiana State University
Andy Clifford, CRESCENT
Alaura Custard, University of Kansas
Marine Denolle, University of Washington
Yoichiro Dobashi, University of Washington
Franklyn Dunbar, Earthscope Consortium
Jill Elizabeth, CRESCENT
Shannon Fasola, CRESCENT
Becky Fildes, Western Washington University
Sofia Franck, University of California - Davis
Alice Gabriel, University of California San Diego
Humberto Alfonso García Montano, UNAN-Managua
Joan Gomberg, United States Geological Survey
Jianhua Gong, Indiana University
Hao Guo, University of Wisconsin - Madison
Shuoshuo Han, The University of Texas at Austin
Ruth Harris, United States Geological Survey
Bin He, University of Oregon
River He, University of Rhode Island
Martin Heesemann, Ocean Networks Canada
Michael Hemmett, University of Washington
Stephan Henneking, The University of Texas at Austin
Jenna Hill, United States Geological Survey
Barry Hirshorn, Scripps Institution of Oceanography / University of California San Diego
Tiegan Hobbs, Geological Survey of Canada / The University of British Columbia / University of Victoria
Emilie Hooft, University of Oregon
Jesse Hutchinson, Ocean Networks Canada
Noel Jackson, University of Kansas
Helen Janiszewski, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa

Hanchao Jian, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution
Lydia Kelley, University of Washington
Harvey Kelsey, Cal Poly Humboldt
Maleen Kidiwela, University of Washington
Zoe Krauss, Pacific Northwest Seismic Network / University of Washington
Fabian Kutschera, Scripps Institution of Oceanography / University of California San Diego
Evan Lahr, University of Washington
Anna Ledeczi, University of Washington
Randall LeVeque, University of Washington
Brad Lipovsky, University of Washington
David Lumley, University of Texas at Dallas
Elizabeth Madden, San José State University
Katie McMartin, Ocean Networks Canada
Tim Melbourne, Central Washington University
Diego Melgar, University of Oregon / CRESCENT
John Myers, The University of Texas at Dallas
Edwin Ndip, University of Buea / Pan African University / University of Ibadan
Yiyu Ni, University of Washington
Andrea Ogston, University of Washington
Bar Oryan, Scripps Institution of Oceanography / University of California San Diego
David Schmidt, University of Washington
David Shelly, United States Geological Survey
Brandon Shuck, Louisiana State University
Buha Mujur Mandela Simamora, Indonesia Agency for Meteorology Climatology and Geophysics
Lynn Simmons, United States Geological Survey
Lydia Staisch, United States Geological Survey
Tianhaozhe Sun, Geological Survey of Canada / University of Victoria
Mika Thompson, University of Washington
Harold Tobin, University of Washington
Anne Trehu, Oregon State University
Man-Yin Tsang, University of Saskatchewan
Kelin Wang, Geological Survey of Canada
Matt Wei, University of Rhode Island
William Wilcock, University of Washington
Ethan Williams, University of California - Santa Cruz
Wenqiang Zhang, Stanford University

Appendix C: Offshore Observations Topical Workshop Feedback Summary

Offshore Observations Topical Workshop Feedback Summary

October 27, 2025

Of the 65 workshop participants, 32 (49%) returned usable survey responses after the workshop, with complete or mostly complete responses to the substantive questions that were asked after the initial self-descriptors at the beginning of the survey. Sample sizes for specific questions may vary slightly since a few people left particular questions unanswered. In some of the following tables, reported percentages may not sum to 100 due to rounding.

In addition to reviewing the tables below that display tabulations of participant responses to fixed-response questions, CRESCENT leaders may find useful information and recommendations by reading each individual comment made by participants in response to the open-ended questions. Some of these will likely resonate or take on additional meaning given background context that is familiar to those with more experience in the CRESCENT scientific and public policy arena. A one-off comment that was given little attention by the evaluator may contain ideas considered important by project staff. Color coding has been applied to highlight identified themes mentioned by multiple survey respondents.

Most of the respondents attended the workshop in person (88%); 12% participated online.

Table 1 displays some key professional characteristics of those participants who responded to the post-workshop survey.

Table 1. Characteristics of Survey Respondents

<p>What is your primary professional role? <i>(mark only one)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50% Research Scientist <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engineering, architecture - Emergency Management 3% Educator or Extension Specialist 28% Student 6% Technician, staff member <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning, Zoning, Regulatory - Spatial Modeling 6% Post-doc 6% Other (specify): <i>"Associate Professor" "Professor"</i>
<p>Which terms best describe your organization? <i>(mark all that apply)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State, regional or local agency 69% University offering related PhD degrees 16% Federal department, agency, or other federal entity 6% Nonprofit organization Public utility 9% University offering related Masters (but not PhD) degrees Private company or industry organization 6% Primarily undergraduate institution (PUI) 3% Minority-serving institution (MSI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Historically Black College or University (HBCU) - Community College - High School or Middle School - Tribal organization 3% Other (specify): <i>"ANSS regional seismic network"</i>

Note. N = 32 responses. Percentages for the first question (primary professional role) may not add to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Table 2 displays participant ratings of the major workshop sessions. The session lengths were rated as "just right" by 80% or more of survey respondents, with the exception of the *Plans for Offshore Observations* session, which was rated as being too short by 25% of those who responded to the survey. For the other sessions, remaining responses were generally divided between "not enough" and "too much" time spent on particular topics.

When asked if the presentations were clear and effective, 94% or more rated each session as being "very effective" or "OK," with the exception of the *Breakout Session*, which was rated as "not very effective" by 14% of respondents. All but two sessions were rated by more than 70% of participants as being "very effective;" lower ratings were given for the *Plans for Offshore Observations* session and especially the *Breakout Session*.

Table 2. Participant Ratings of Workshop Session Length and Effectiveness

For each session within the workshop, please choose one answer for each of the two questions on the right. (leave a row blank if you did not attend that specific session)		Amount of time spent on topic:			Was the presentation clear and effective?		
		Not enough	Just right	Too much	Not very effective	OK	Very effective
A1	Fluid Pathways and Hydrology of Subduction Zones	6 %	91	3	-	22 %	78
A2	Constraints on Megathrust Locking State and Shallow Slow Slip	3	94	3	-	19	81
A3	Accretionary Wedge Deformation	13	84	3	3	16	81
A4	Structure of the Incoming Plate	6	94	-	3	25	72
A5	Plans for Future Offshore Observations	25	75	-	6	31	63
A6	Breakout Session	10	80	10	14	50	36

Note. N = 32 responses. Each row of numbers contains the proportion (percentage) of participants who gave each response to the two questions listed at the top. Row percentages within the columns for each question may not add to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Table 3 lists verbatim comments offered by survey respondents about the strengths or weaknesses of the workshop sessions. There were many positive comments including several praising the format and content of the sessions along with a suggestion to improve this in the future by focusing the lightning talks on more narrow topics. Comments or recommendations about workshop weaknesses were generally about not having enough time for particular activities. Other individual comments or suggestions in Table 3 may be particularly interesting or helpful for future planning.

Table 3. Participant Comments on Workshop Sessions

A7	<p>Please add comments about the strengths or weaknesses of the <u>specific workshop sessions</u> listed above: <i>(later you will have a chance to comment on the workshop as a whole)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>I thought the keynote and lightning talks format and diversity of topics were great!</i> ▪ <i>It was great but rather rushed.</i> ▪ <i>Loved the fruit served all day! Great collection of talks, liked the short talks. Breakout could have been skipped for having more time to ask questions after every talk.</i> ▪ <i>The alternation between short, extended lightning-style talks and longer-version talk was excellent!</i> ▪ <i>Really a well-run workshop overall. I got a lot out of it and would not recommend any major changes. The one minor change I would suggest is more time for networking, either structured or unstructured.</i> ▪ <i>I really liked the workshop in terms of how it helped people who work on different fields/topics studying the Cascadia subduction zone to share knowledge and learn from each other and build potential collaborations.</i> ▪ <i>Would have been nice to have longer to more comprehensively synthesize and respond to the breakout session responses though I realize this can be done asynchronously once notes are compiled for the workshop report.</i> ▪ <i>I was disappointed that the feedback from multiple breakouts was not shared with the whole group. The discussion at the end of the day was very limited and it wasn't at all clear what was accomplished by the meeting, what people felt were key priorities or what the OO-SIG might set as a goal for the next year.</i> ▪ <i>Good and I love it.</i> ▪ <i>Nice balance of topics.</i> ▪ <i>I felt like the session topics were able to cover most of the subjects that folks in attendance work on, which was great!</i> ▪ <i>I really enjoy the geochemistry Keynote talk in the Fluid Pathways and Hydrology of Subduction Zones session. This kind of cross-disciplinary perspective is great.</i> ▪ <i>Strengths: talks were just the right duration and scientifically very rich.</i> ▪ <i>The lack of access to free seismic databases for my country and a bit of the language barrier.</i> ▪ <i>It was a great conference my dudes.</i> ▪ <i>The accretionary wedge deformation workshop was very informative, especially Harold Tobin's talk. The structure of the talk was very easy to follow and went through each section with cohesion. I think most lightning talks were harder to digest as they had too broad a topic for only a 3 minute talk, so maybe try and have talks on more specific areas or topics rather than a whole investigation overview.</i>
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Table 4 displays participant ratings of the workshop as a whole. More than 90% of respondents “strongly” or “moderately” agreed that *the content was consistent with the publicized description (100%), the workshop furthered my understanding of the state of offshore research on the Cascadia Subduction Zone (97%), the workshop outreach, invitation and structure helped me feel welcome and valued as a participant (92%), and I would recommend this workshop to others (97%).*

Almost 80% of the survey respondents also “strongly” or “moderately” agreed that *The workshop helped identify gaps in our knowledge of the Cascadia Subduction Zone and next steps to fill these gaps (79%).*

Weaker ratings were given to three statements: *The workshop helped clarify how I or my organization can contribute to or participate in offshore research on subduction zone questions (72% “moderately” or “strongly” agreed), the workshop was well-balanced between content delivery and participatory activities (68%); and I had ample opportunity to network and build relationships with representatives of other organizations that are relevant to my work (72%).*

Table 4. Participant Ratings of the Workshop as a Whole

Questions about the workshop as a whole: Please choose one answer in each row:		Strongly Disagree	Moderately Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Moderately Agree	Strongly Agree
B1	The content was consistent with the publicized description.	3 %	-	-	-	20	77
B2	The workshop furthered my understanding of the state of offshore research on the Cascadia Subduction Zone.	3	-	-	-	13	83
B3	The workshop helped identify gaps in our knowledge of the Cascadia Subduction Zone and next steps to fill these gaps.	-	3	-	17	38	41
B4	The workshop helped clarify how I or my organization can contribute to or participate in offshore research on subduction zone questions.	-	7	3	17	31	41
B5	The workshop was well-balanced between content delivery and participatory activities.	4	-	14	14	18	50
B6	I had ample opportunity to network and build relationships with representatives of other organizations that are relevant to my work.	4	4	7	14	43	29
B7	The workshop outreach, invitation and structure helped me feel welcome and valued as a participant.	4	-	-	4	36	57
B8	I would recommend this workshop to others.	3	-	-	-	17	80

Note. N = 28 to 30 responses. Each row of numbers contains the proportion (percentage) of participants who gave each response to the question. Row percentages may not add to exactly 100% due to rounding.

Table 5 displays comments on overall workshop strengths. Themes included positive notes on the format and organization that mixed in-depth and lightning talks, the small meeting format and participant group that helped make the discussions more focused, the science content, the networking opportunities, and the robust participation of early career researchers..

Table 5. Participant Comments on Workshop Strengths

C1	<p>What was good about this workshop?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diversity of topics, organization. ▪ I appreciate the clear organization and welcome comments from the reception. ▪ Randomly assigned breakout groups are excellent for meeting new community members. ▪ Many presentations from early-career researchers. ▪ Great topics and talks. ▪ Format and organization was great! ▪ Only followed over Zoom, but could follow very well and enjoyed all sessions, even the ones that were less close to my expertise. ▪ Varying shorter and longer talks was great! ▪ The balance between presentations and networking. ▪ The size and number of people, the rapid fire talks. ▪ Passion and energy of the early career workshop planning committee. Well thought out sessions and speakers driven by state of the scientific understanding. Effective presentation format for rapidly bringing the interdisciplinary community up to speed. ▪ Talks were really informative. ▪ Meeting people in this field. ▪ I liked that the sessions were organized topically and not methodically. It was useful and I think made for better Q and A and discussion to have the sessions organized in this way: Think about a specific topic, and have a sampling of talks from different subdisciplines each thinking about the same general large-scale topic. I also liked that each session had the longer talk followed by lightning talks and Q and A. It kept things engaging, allowed us to hear short but effective updates from a lot of community members (across career stages), and again I think lead to good Q and A and discussion. I also think having lunch all together in the same room allowed for more networking and discussion amongst attendees which is really great for small workshops like this. ▪ Great to bring everyone together. ▪ I think the organizers did a great job of balancing talks between topics and talk length to give everyone a broad overview of the things we're all working on. Doing so set us up well to engage in the breakout sessions at the end. ▪ I experienced good involvement of young students/postdocs in this workshop. ▪ The science content was overall great. The way these sessions covering a specific aspects of the offshore subduction system in a mutually related way is very good. I also like the combination of relatively long and short talks. ▪ The parts that I saw were great. The fact that it was small with many people that have engaged in offshore research in this region is great. It was too bad that our USGS peers couldn't attend. ▪ Excellent workshop, I learned more at this workshop than at the annual meeting. ▪ Science talks went deep. I also enjoyed having lots of talk sessions rather than long breakout discussions. I was unable to attend the breakout discussion at the end due to another meeting at the same time. ▪ The speakers and the presenters. ▪ I liked that it was a smaller workshop, made it easier to connect with everyone I wanted to connect to. I really enjoyed the plans for future offshore observations topic, really highlighted the current research going on currently. ▪ I liked the lightning style for the talks. It made it so most of the presenters didn't get too lost in the weeds when explaining their work. I felt like I understood more of what everyone was doing. Even if they did get too technical for me, I was only lost for 5-10 minutes, and had time to ask questions after. ▪ There were a large variety of topics that helped my understanding of offshore observations of Cascadia, especially as someone who is just starting research on the area. I also liked that there were talks on the Nankai trough which helped put other similar subduction zones into perspective.
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Table 6 presents verbatim suggestions for improvement, along with some additional positive comments. Many comments suggested a longer meeting with more time for both scientific content and networking. Other individual recommendations may also provide actionable suggestions for future workshops.

Table 6. Participant Suggestions for Improvement

C2	Any suggestions for improvement? Consider length, timing, location, venue, facilitation, structure, and content.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>To prepare some paper boxes and an announcement to prevent enormous food waste.</i> ▪ <i>1 day is really short.</i> ▪ <i>Wish there was more time for questions.</i> ▪ <i>No, great scientific content!</i> ▪ <i>Venue: the coffee was taken away a bit early.</i> ▪ <i>Slightly longer talks (10 minutes?) But somehow without reducing the speakers or making the meeting longer. Maybe without the "keynotes" for each section? But the selected format was not bad overall. Main thing I wished for was more time to network with others at the meeting.</i> ▪ <i>The talks can be a little longer (most talks are 5 minutes only).</i> ▪ <i>Great to build this around the Annual Meeting for efficiency of travel. Hub seemed to work well as a venue. Catering, hotel and CRESCENT hosting all on point. Would have like to have seen more of a structure around capturing the consensus for next steps and consideration of opportunities for external partnerships and funding. Presentations from industry and/or oceanographic disciplines could be interesting perspectives to capture for next iteration of this workshop.</i> ▪ <i>Direct breakout groups to do introductions. My graduate student ended up in a group of 4 senior scientists who did not introduce themselves and did not attempt to include her in the discussion in any way.</i> ▪ <i>Maybe two days would be nice with more in depth presentations.</i> ▪ <i>We could promote more international parties for participation.</i> ▪ <i>There was a green line on the projected screen the whole time - sometime a little distracting. Hopefully this type of technical minor issue can be eliminated next time.</i> ▪ <i>I did not attend long enough. The parts I saw were great. The venue worked well.</i> ▪ <i>Ease of use of data for each geographical area.</i> ▪ <i>Having longer talks at the beginning of the topic and then several smaller ones made it hard for me to digest what everyone was trying to present on. If there are enough talks I would prefer the workshop to be 2 days instead of 1 day so that everyone has enough time to properly present their topic. Next time I would love to see more presentations on Earthquake Early Warning, this was notably absent from the workshop.</i> ▪ <i>We had a pretty busy day, so there wasn't much time for networking outside of the tables we sat at or the groups we were in for the discussion. Maybe a dinner would be helpful? Not necessarily that CRESCENT pay for dinner, but a "hey we're meeting for dinner here, feel free to come" but we're each responsible for our own food and drinks.</i> ▪ <i>The lightning talks should be more focused so there is less to digest in 3 minutes. When presented, as an online participant it is hard to see what the presenter is pointing at when discussing a figure, so next time it would be helpful to use the mouse laser pointer to help out online participants as well.</i>

Table 7 displays verbatim participant comments about challenges they face in Cascadia subduction zone research. In addition to potentially useful individual comments, three themes were related to the need for more data, seismic velocity models and 3D models, and use of ocean bottom pressure gauges.

Table 7. Participant Comments on Challenges in Cascadia Subduction Zone Research

C3	What are some of the biggest challenges you face in your work related to the Cascadia subduction zone, and how could that work benefit from CRESCENT-related science?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>There is a vast amount of research on Cascadia, so meetings like this, when research is exchanged and discussed, are very helpful.</i> ▪ <i>Evaluation of the geodetic signal-to-noise ratio of ocean bottom pressure gauges.</i> ▪ <i>I can learn a lot from users of borehole pressure gauges.</i> ▪ <i>Funding. More seed grants.</i> ▪ <i>Not enough data, collaboration on where/how we are collecting data.</i> ▪ <i>A better seismic velocity model will result in better heterogenous elastic Green's Functions offshore.</i> ▪ <i>Interpreting my seismic velocity models in terms of offshore geology is challenging. I did learn a lot from this workshop.</i> ▪ <i>Learning about what is known or not known.</i> ▪ <i>Data availability.</i> ▪ <i>Support for collaborative writing of proposals.</i> ▪ <i>We detect and locate earthquakes. The continued improvement of knowledge of the 3D structure will be extremely useful once we are set up to do our routine earthquake locations in a 3D model. We currently produce very poor locations for events that are offshore, even for events that are relatively near-shore. Using a more sophisticated regional Earth structure model should help determine whether offshore simplicity is likely to be associated with the megathrust, etc.</i> ▪ <i>The need for data from my region to conduct research and/or use in my geophysics classes.</i> ▪ <i>I think international collaboration is the big challenge. CRESCENT provides an opportunity for organizations from Canada and the US to talk and collaborate.</i> ▪ <i>I want more offshore observations so bad. I really want more continuous seafloor data, like borehole, OBS, anything that records more frequently than GNSS-A (no hate to GNSS-A, just 5 data points does not make a very reliable time series).</i>

The final survey question asked for recommendations on facilitating interorganizational collaboration. Verbatim responses are listed in Table 8. Two prominent themes were continuing to convene meetings and workshops and otherwise facilitating logistical coordination of efforts, communication, and funding.

Table 8. Participant Recommendations for Collaboration on Offshore Observations

C4	How can CRESCENT best facilitate interorganizational collaboration on offshore observations?
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Annual meetings, research updates.</i> ▪ <i>To involve some oceanographers as potential speakers.</i> ▪ <i>What are the noise sources, amplitude, and frequency for OBS, OBP, DAS, and GNSS-A?</i> ▪ <i>Workshops?</i> ▪ <i>Coordination.</i> ▪ <i>Make a database of people and projects involved in different projects that may point to who might be working on similar areas of interest.</i> ▪ <i>I think the workshop was excellent, it should happen regularly.</i> ▪ <i>Right now I think the main thing CRESCENT can do is logistical - listing all the various offshore observations and their statuses (ongoing, completed, data availability, etc.) in one place would be a big community benefit.</i> ▪ <i>in person and online workshop? Organize more regular short zoom meetings?</i> ▪ <i>Seek input from external partners (infrastructure, industry, oceanography, coastal planners, emergency managers). The group decided that the webinar space is saturated in terms of using that medium for keeping folks up to speed with developments and spoke in favor of an annualized in person meeting. Offering a remote option and/or moving the location of the meeting to allow equitable participation would be prudent. Could also consider offering guest webinars in other established webinar series to share ideas and gain different perspectives, e.g. considering applications of OO to other users and presenting in their forums, e.g. COPEs Hub, Cascadia Lifelines Program, EERI, EarthScope.</i> ▪ <i>Know people in this field.</i> ▪ <i>I think this type of workshop made for a lot of connections between community members, and having it attached to the Annual meeting worked well so that we could continue some of those conversations over the following few days while we were still in person.</i> ▪ <i>Spearhead community proposals.</i> ▪ <i>Having workshops like these.</i> ▪ <i>Access to seismic databases for the subduction zone of the Central American Plate.</i> ▪ <i>Getting everyone into the same room is a really big step. Maybe we could have an offshore observations slack or email list? Some way to facilitate communication among different organizations and individuals outside of the one day we're all in the same town.</i>